

ICT requirements and data management of the pilots

WP2, T2.3

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Executive summary

This document, Deliverable ***D2.3 ICT requirements and data management of the pilots*** of the eLITHE project (project reference: 101138325), reports the results of Task T2.3 ***Identification of ICT infrastructure needs and definition of data architecture***.

The report presents the requirements identified for the development and implementation of the eLITHE Platform, as well as the methodology followed for this purpose. It describes the system functionalities that will be delivered to the end-users packed into the tool, while defining the datasets that will feed each module and the ones that will be produced as a result of their operation. This deliverable also defines the high-level data management strategies that will be followed for each one of the project pilot sites.

Additionally, this document presents an IT and data architecture, emphasizing interoperability with both legacy and newly designed equipment. It also maps data sources, storage services, the Platform's main engines and how this information is going to be presented to the end-user through the graphic user interfaces.

The delivery of this deliverable is done in accordance to the description in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A with no time deviation and no content deviation from the original planning.

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ACRONYM LIST

Table 1. Acronyms List

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DB	Database
DPM	Discrete Phase Model
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSS	Decision Support System
DT	Digital Twin
ESB	Enterprise Service Bus
FMU	Functional Mockup Unit
GUI	Graphic User Interface
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
LHV	Lower Heating Value
MW	Microwave
NEMO	Nominated Electricity Market Operator
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PV	Photovoltaic

Req	Requirement
ROM	Reduced Order Model
RPM	Revolutions Per Minute
RT	Real-time
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SO	System Operator
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TESS	Thermal Energy Storage System
UDF	User-Defined Function
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document aims to report the outcomes of T2.3. The objectives of the report are to describe the main IT requirements, control features, systems functionalities, data models and parameters to be monitored while ensuring cohesive data exchange between the different modules of the tool to be implemented during the demonstration campaigns on the three pilots considered in eLITHE, the Spanish site pilot (TCD pilot), Greek site pilot (METLEN pilot) and German site pilot (IZF pilot).

1.2 Scope of the document

This document addresses the preparatory work for the development of the eLITHE Platform, serving as a landing process to start WP3 on Digitalization, control and flexibility tools of the electrification processes. By addressing technical, architectural, and data management aspects, this document sets a solid foundation for the kick-off of the upcoming development activities.

1.3 Structure of the document

The document starts its core structure in section 2.1 with the presentation of the methodology applied to come up with the current list of 46 main IT requirements for the development and implementation of the tool. This part is followed by the presentation of each one of the requirements summarised and labelled into standardised tables in section 2.2.

After that, the document is followed by the description of the produced ICT and data architecture that will drive the development of the eLITHE Platform in section 3, along with the description of each one of the engines/modules involved, identifying the necessary input datasets for their execution and the results that they will produce in section 4.

The document concludes with section 5 presenting the approach that is to be followed in terms of data management strategies for each one of the pilots and it is wrapped up with the conclusions in section 6.

2 Main functional and technical project requirements for the implementation of the eLITHE Platform

2.1 Methodology followed

The specification of system or product requirements is a key activity before its design and production. The formal definition of a product's requirements is the following: "The requirements should encompass associated constraints and conditions with the purpose to transform through their analysis the stakeholder, requirement-driven view of desired services into a technical view of a required product that could deliver those services." (ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2011).

Especially, in software products the requirements include the features and functionalities that the end-users demand from the specific product and thus their identification is of the utmost importance for the successful implementation of a useful and user-friendly product. The requirements can be obvious or hidden, known or unknown, expected or unexpected from the client's point of view. Gathering the requirements from all stakeholders in a project is a key success factor.

In addition to describing the expected characteristics of a product, the requirements identification process reveals conflicting features and helps resolve them. For the effective implementation of this important procedure, the Volere methodology [1] was chosen.

An important characteristic of the Volere methodology is its simplicity. It requires simple steps to identify and formalize the requirements in an unambiguous manner. Moreover, it provides an easy process to track and evaluate the progress of the requirements' elicitation procedure. Besides being efficient and easy to use, the Volere methodology provides a mechanism for all partners to specify the requirements in a standard format. Thereby, specifying additional context of a requirement such as the rationale and the acceptance criteria for every requirement helps to build a common understanding of the overall system. Furthermore, defining priorities helps to clarify the focus of the project.

This last feature of prioritization is of special importance. In order to prioritize requirements, the Volere platform offers a scale from 1 to 5 corresponding to low and high-priority requirements respectively. The prioritization of requirements is a very important analysis technique since the success of the project can be assessed with respect to the realization of the high-priority requirements. The requirements with medium or low priority, however, are not of immediate relevance to the project. Their realization may provide additional features or benefits for applications or users.

Using the Volere methodology, as it is implemented in an online platform developed by ETRA, the consortium has proceeded to the identification of 46 requirements for the eLITHE

Platform that will be developed in the context of the project. If more requirements relevant enough to be formalised with the Volere methodology are identified and validated during Work Package 3, they will be reported under deliverable D3.4 eLITHE Digital Platform.

2.1.1 Volere tool

For the definition of a complete list of requirements, a web tool based on the Volere methodology was developed by ETRA.

For security reasons, the access to the web tool has been restricted to authorized users. Invitations have been sent by the Task Leader, who also acts as the platform administrator, to all the involved partners of that task to fill in the registration form requesting a valid username and password (Figure 1). This request is processed by the administrator who decides who must be granted access to the website.

The image shows a registration form titled "Volere" with a logo featuring a lightbulb. The form is titled "Registration" and includes the instruction: "Please, fill in the registration form and a username-password will be sent to you as soon as possible." The form contains several input fields: "Name*" (text input), "Organization*" (dropdown menu), "E-mail*" (text input), "Phone" (text input), and "Username*" (text input). Below the fields, there is a note "* Required fields" and two buttons: "Save" and "Cancel".

Figure 1. Website Registration Form

If the administrator approves the request, an email with the username and password is sent to the requester. From that moment, the user will be able to access the eLITHE requirements definition website through the Login page (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Login

Access to the web tool is granted after successful authentication. The application allows the administrator to manage the validation process, from the initial definition to the final list of requirements, including validation and revision stages.

2.1.1.1 Specification process

The overall Volere process, supported by the web tool, is as follows. After an initial specification of requirements, the users can specify conflicts, dependencies and objections. Users can iteratively revise the specification and identify additional issues until it is free of conflicts, dependencies and objections. The result constitutes the final list of requirements. The following subsections briefly outline the individual steps.

2.1.1.2 Requirement definition

In the first stage, all the requirements needed to accomplish the project objectives must be defined. These will be refined in future stages. The most useful information and the main functionalities at this stage are available on the homepage (Figure 3):

The screenshot shows the Volere Tool interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Introduction', 'Requirements', and 'User account'. Below this is a progress bar with stages: 'DEFINITION OF REQUIREMENTS', 'VALIDATION', 'REVISION', 'VALIDATION', 'REVISION', 'VALIDATION', 'REVISION', 'VALIDATION', 'REVISION', 'VALIDATION', 'REVISION', and 'CLOSED'. The 'Requirements list' section is active, showing a table of requirements. The table has columns for ID, Description, Classification, Type, Priority, and Author. The requirements listed include: Unique ID, eLITHE Platform 3D visualization, eLITHE Platform real-time parameters, eLITHE Platform flexibility market participation, eLITHE Platform real-time gas and electricity consumption, eLITHE Platform forecasting module, eLITHE Platform remuneration sensor, eLITHE Platform health index, eLITHE Platform early detection, and eLITHE Platform hourly energy flexibility potential.

ID	Description	Classification	Type	Priority	Author
Unique ID	A one-sentence statement of the intention of the requirement	The classification group which the requirement belongs to	The type from the template	Priority	Author of the requirement
Pi01_Gen_012	The eLITHE Platform will provide a 3D-visualisation of the plant, which will allow to monitor real-time parameters as well as to explore simulation scenarios from the DES.	eLITHE Platform General	Usability and humanity requirements	★★★★★	ETRA (Radovan Desislavski)
Pi01_Gen_011	The "flexibility market participation" module will use the total flexibility forecast and the economic benefit of the implicit flexibility calculated by the DES tool as the energy and price thresholds of a market-organized explicit flexibility event participation	eLITHE Platform General	Functional and data requirements	★★★★★	CRCE (Juan Antonio Aranda Usón)
Pi01_Gen_010	The DES module will require real-time gas and electricity consumption, production-rate, production target, PV generation, BESS charging status, demand and generation forecasts for the following 24 hours, as well as the energy costs from the "remuneration scenario" module. More specifically: Real-time gas and electricity consumption in kWh for the last hour Production rate and production target in kWh for the last hour PV generation in kW during the last hour BESS last State of Charge Demand and generation forecasts for the following 24 hours, in kWh per each of the following 24 h Energy costs from the "remuneration scenario" module, in €/kWh-in-VAT included Actual process temperature and target process temperature in Celsius	eLITHE Platform General	Functional and data requirements	★★★★★	CRCE (Juan Antonio Aranda Usón)
Pi01_Gen_009	The Forecasting Module will need hourly historic energy consumption and generation profiles for at least 3 months in kWh.	eLITHE Platform General	Functional and data requirements	★★★★★	CRCE (Juan Antonio Aranda Usón)
Pi01_Gen_008	The "Remuneration Sensor" module will require the energy term of the hourly market tariffs applicable to the electricity and gas supply in €/MWh (incl. VAT). In case of ToU tariffs, the hourly energy cost should be indexed to a 24h-ahead pool market.	eLITHE Platform General	Functional and data requirements	★★★★★	CRCE (Juan Antonio Aranda Usón)
Pi01_Gen_007	The eLITHE Platform will display the health index of the integrated assets (furnaces)	eLITHE Platform General	The scope of the product	★★★★★	ETRA (Esteban Pastor Calatayud)
Pi01_Gen_006	Based on the retrieved data the eLITHE Platform should be able to identify failures in the furnaces in Real Time.	eLITHE Platform General	The scope of the product	★★★★★	ETRA (Esteban Pastor Calatayud)
Pi01_Gen_005	The eLITHE platform should provide early detection of potential faults in the equipment	eLITHE Platform General	The scope of the product	★★★★★	ETRA (Radovan Desislavski)
Pi01_Gen_004	The DES tool shall calculate and aggregate the hourly energy flexibility potential of the process from different sources for the day ahead, and provide this output to the local flexibility market participation tool	eLITHE Platform General	Functional and data requirements	★★★★★	CRCE (Juan Antonio Aranda Usón)
Pi01_Gen_003	The DES tool shall calculate and aggregate the hourly energy flexibility potential of the process from different sources for the day ahead, and provide this output to the local flexibility market participation tool	eLITHE Platform General	Functional and data requirements	★★★★★	CRCE (Juan Antonio Aranda Usón)

Figure 3. Volere Tool Homepage

- **Help:** An external link to the Volere requirements specification template.
- **List of requirements:** The list of requirements with some additional options.
 - Filtering options: The list of requirements filtered by id, type and/or author.
 - Expand table: Show/hide some columns, displaying more or less information about the requirement.
- **Requirements management:** Modification options for requirements.
 - View a requirement
 - Edit a requirement (only available for the author)
 - Delete a requirement (only available for the author)
- **Requirements' tracing:** After the first validation, a new service is made available for keeping track of all the requirements history.
- **Export to CSV:** Export all requirements to a CSV file for external handling.
- **Insert a new requirement:** Opens a new window (Figure 4) to allow adding a new requirement. All the fields are required except for "Comments" which is optional.

New requirement

Please, insert as many requirements as missing information on the project requirements list. These requirements will be validated on the following iteration.

The screenshot shows a 'New requirement' form with the following fields:

- Classification:** A dropdown menu.
- Description:** A text input field with a small icon on the right.
- Type:** A dropdown menu.
- Priority:** A field containing five stars (☆☆☆☆☆).
- Rationale:** A text input field with a small icon on the right.
- Acceptance criteria:** A text input field.
- Comments:** A text input field with a small icon on the right.

At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: 'Create' and 'Cancel'.

Figure 4. Definition of Requirements

The required fields are:

1. **ID:** Appended by an automatically generated sequential number, this ID uniquely identifies each requirement.
2. **Classification:** The requirements are classified according to the applicable Pilot.
3. **Description:** A one-sentence statement which describes the intention of the requirement. Its syntax is one of the following:
 - a. [Condition] [Subject] [Action] [Object] [Constraint]
EXAMPLE: When signal x is received [Condition], the system [Subject] shall set [Action] the signal x received bit [Object] within 2 seconds [Constraint].
 - b. [Condition] [Action or Constraint] [Value]
EXAMPLE: At sea state 1 [Condition], the Radar System shall detect targets at ranges out to [Action or Constraint] 100 nautical miles [Value].
 - c. [Subject] [Action] [Value]
EXAMPLE: The Invoice System [Subject], shall display pending customer invoices [Action] in ascending order [Value] in which invoices are to be paid.
4. **Type:** The type of the requirement as defined by VoleRe.
5. **Rationale:** A justification of the requirement.
6. **Acceptance criteria:** A measurement (quantitative or qualitative) to verify that the solution meets the original requirement.
EXAMPLE:

Requirement: The eLITHE Platform will display the health index of the integrated assets (furnaces)

Acceptance criteria: 0% health index coincident with failure

7. **Priority** The importance for the customer of successfully implementing the requirement.

2.1.1.3 Requirement Validation

After the initial definition of requirements, the validation process begins. All the requirements should be approved by all the users. At this stage, conflicts and dependencies between requirements must be detected. Furthermore, any objection must be pointed out:

- **Dependency:** Requirements that have some dependency on other requirements.
- **Conflict:** Requirements that cannot be implemented if another requirement is implemented or a conflict due to an insufficient definition of the requirement.
- **Objection:** A reason or argument offered in disagreement, opposition, refusal or disapproval of the requirement.

2.1.1.4 Requirement revision

According to the Volere methodology, after the validation procedure, the revision procedure is to be implemented. The activities of the revision procedure are listed below.

During the revision process, dependencies, conflicts and objections identified during validation are solved. However, if the authors do not agree with the validator's opinion, then they can make use of the "Reviser's comments" option to point out their disagreement or clarify the intention of the requirement. Note that only the authors of the requirements that have to be revised are able to add comments to the dependency, conflict or objection.

The checkboxes in "Requirements revised" column and "Validator's approval" column help the users to check the status of the revision and together with the possibility of adding comments facilitate the interaction and communication between the author and the validator. For security reasons, the checkboxes on the "Requirements revised" column are only enabled for the authors of the requirements who have also enabled the possibility of adding comments. Moreover, for the same reason, the checkboxes on the "Validator's approval" column are enabled only for the author of the validation.

The revision process consists of four steps:

- First, the authors should identify which requirements have been objected to or are involved in any conflict or dependency.
- Second and after analysing the validator's opinion:
 - The author may agree with the validator and proceed to modify or delete the requirement.
 - The author may disagree with the validator; therefore he/she should make appropriate comments trying to clarify the requirement with a better explanation or justify the intention of the requirement.

- Third, the author should mark the checkbox of the requirement as revised.

Finally, the validator reviews the revised requirements and approves the actions taken by the author to resolve the dependency/conflict/objection.

2.2 Final set of requirements for the implementation of the eLITHE Platform

In this Section, a high-level presentation of the eLITHE Platform's requirements is provided. An initial classification of the requirements is based on the corresponding applicable Pilots (tables 2 to 47). A total of 46 requirements have been identified.

Table 2. eLITHE platform requirement #1 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #1
[Description]	The Alarm Generation module should generate alarms when an abnormal value is detected in a parameter.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE Platform should inform the plant operator in RT of any potential alert that may be a danger or that may disrupt the normal operation of the plant.
[Acceptance criteria]	Pop-up alert posted within seconds after the identification of the abnormal parameter value.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 3. eLITHE platform requirement #2 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #2
[Description]	The DSS tool shall forecast the thermal energy costs and the available flexibility sources to provide an hourly optimal energy management recommendation in economic terms.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements.
[Rationale]	An hourly optimal energy management recommendation is key for the implementation of an optimised operation plan and feeds the rest of services that aim at improving the plant operator's daily business.

[Acceptance criteria]	Hourly energy management recommendations provided to the plant operator on a daily basis.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 4. eLITHE platform requirement #3 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #3
[Description]	The DSS tool shall calculate the day-ahead energy operation costs of the optimal energy strategy and the default scenario to assess the potential economic savings derived from the implementation of the strategy.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements.
[Rationale]	The hourly optimal energy management recommendation must take into account as a key input the economic terms. These results are key for the implementation of an optimised operation plan and feed the rest of services that aim at improving the plant operator's daily business.
[Acceptance criteria]	Daily delivery of the day-ahead energy operation costs including the potential economic savings derived from the implementation of the strategy.
Priority	4
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot.

Table 5. eLITHE platform requirement #4 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #4
[Description]	The DSS tool shall calculate and aggregate the hourly energy flexibility potential of the process from different sources for the day ahead, and provide this output to the local flexibility market participation tool.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements

[Rationale]	In line with the previous requirement, the DSS should also provide the available flexibility each hour for the Local Flexibility Market participation module to make use of it.
[Acceptance criteria]	Daily delivery of the day-ahead energy operation costs including the available flexibility along with its linked cost.
Priority	4
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 6. eLITHE platform requirement #5 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #5
[Description]	The eLITHE platform should provide early detection of potential faults in the equipment.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The predictive maintenance module anticipates failures in certain parts of the installation before they occur. This analysis is done based on multiple data parameters retrieved and offers the plant operator the possibility to plan maintenance activities in advance and reduce the downtime cost.
[Acceptance criteria]	Alert with eventual failure and its probability.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot

Table 7. eLITHE platform requirement #6 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #6
[Description]	Based on the retrieved data, the eLITHE Platform should be able to identify failures in the furnaces in Real Time.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE Platform will display failure alarms (identified by the furnace SCADA or not) to reinforce the self-learning algorithm.

[Acceptance criteria]	RT alerts with a close-to-100% probability of occurrence based on the predictive maintenance algorithm.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot

Table 8. eLITHE platform requirement #7 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #7
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform will display the health index of the integrated assets (furnaces)
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The health index will be linked to the possible generated alarms and will be measured as a percentage.
[Acceptance criteria]	A health index of 0% coincides with failure
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot

Table 9. eLITHE platform requirement #8 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #8
[Description]	The "Remuneration Scenarios" module will require the energy term of the hourly market tariffs applicable to the electricity and gas supply in €/kWh (no VAT). In the case of ToU tariffs, the hourly energy cost should be indexed to a 24-hour-ahead pool market.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	The optimal energy management of the thermal system carried out by the DSS is cost-driven for every hour of the day ahead. This input in €/kWh is provided by the "Remuneration Scenarios" module. The "Remuneration Scenarios" module will provide the most likely day ahead hourly electricity and gas costs for a full year time frame, in €/kWh VAT excluded, either from the 24h matching of the spot market auctions or from the fixed hourly value of the applicable market tariffs.

[Acceptance criteria]	A full year of hourly energy costs per energy source and carrier for market tariffs and the 24-hour-ahead energy prices for indexed pool markets.
Priority	4
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 10. eLITHE platform requirement #9 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #9
[Description]	The Forecasting Module will need hourly historic energy consumption and generation profiles for at least 3 months in kWh.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	Forecasts are based on historic trained data sets for generation and demand, both electricity and gas.
[Acceptance criteria]	Data provided representing 3 months in kWh.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 11. eLITHE platform requirement #10 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #10
[Description]	<p>The DSS module will require real-time gas and electricity consumption, production rate, production target, PV generation, BESS charging status, demand and generation forecasts for the following 24 hours, as well as the energy costs from the "remuneration scenarios" module. More specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time gas and electricity consumption in kWh for the last hour • Production rate and production target in kg/h for the last hour • PV generation in kW during the last hour. • BESS last State of Charge • Demand and generation forecasts for the following 24 hours, in kWh per each of the following 24 h

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy costs from the "remuneration scenarios" module. In €/kWh no VAT is included. • Actual process temperature and target process temperature in Celsius
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	The "DSS and flexibility forecasting" module will provide the energy flexibility forecast for the following 24 h, and for the hour ahead in kWh, as well as the optimal energy management and economic savings of the implicit use of the flexibility usage in €/h.
[Acceptance criteria]	The listed parameters must be displayed in RT with the agreed units and updating granularity.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 12. eLITHE platform requirement #11 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #11
[Description]	The "flexibility market participation" module will use the total flexibility forecast and the economic benefit of the implicit flexibility calculated by the DSS tool as the energy and price thresholds of a market-triggered explicit flexibility event participation.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	The calculated flexibility for the hour ahead can either be used internally, benefitting from hourly energy cost differences, or externally to be offered as a response to a demand response market signal. The market participation tool will support in the decision of where to use this flexibility. This tool will receive signals from the DR market and evaluate the eligibility to take part in the event based on the amount of available flexibility for the next hour and the expected benefit of using the flexibility internally.
[Acceptance criteria]	Simulation-based results considering the usage of the available flexibility.
Priority	4
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 13. eLITHE platform requirement #12 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #12
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform will provide a 3D visualisation of the plant, which will allow to monitor real-time parameters as well as to explore simulation scenarios from the DTs.
[Type]	Usability and humanity requirements
[Rationale]	The 3D visualisation provides an improved comprehension of the plant.
[Acceptance criteria]	The 3D visualisation should provide an intuitive and clear representation of the plant and its status using visual indicators (such as colour codes).
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot

Table 14. eLITHE platform requirement #13 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #13
[Description]	A middleware will be deployed to collect the real-time data from the pilots and store it in the platform's databases.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	The monitored data of the pilots must be accessible to all platform modules that need it.
[Acceptance criteria]	Pilots' data is stored and available for retrieval.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot, METLEN Pilot, IZF Pilot

Table 15. eLITHE platform requirement #14 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #14
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the total electrical consumption of the furnace in kW in RT.
[Type]	The scope of the product

[Rationale]	The plant operator should constantly be able to monitor the consumed power by the piloted electrical furnace.
[Acceptance criteria]	The electrical power must be updated with a granularity of 1 minute.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 16. eLITHE platform requirement #15 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #15
[Description]	The eLITHE platform should provide, simultaneously with the furnace consumption, the local PV generation.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on local PV generation displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 17. eLITHE platform requirement #16 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #16
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the flow of natural gas from each burner.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on natural gas flow displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 18. eLITHE platform requirement #17 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #17
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the flow of oxygen of each burner.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on oxygen flow displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 19. eLITHE platform requirement #18 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #18
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the pressure of the natural gas of each burner.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on natural gas pressure displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 20. eLITHE platform requirement #19 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #19
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the massflow of the raw materials in kg/h.
[Type]	The scope of the product

[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on raw material massflow displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 21. eLITHE platform requirement #20 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #20
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the massflow of the final product in kg/h.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the massflow of the final product displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 22. eLITHE platform requirement #21 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #21
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the electric consumption of the electrodes.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the electricity consumption of the electrodes must be displayed continuously.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 23. eLITHE platform requirement #22 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #22
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the electrical consumption of the induction system.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on electricity consumption of the induction system displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 24. eLITHE platform requirement #23 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #23
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the electrical consumption of the auxiliary equipment.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on electricity consumption of the auxiliary equipment displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 25. eLITHE platform requirement #24 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #24
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the internal temperature of the furnace.
[Type]	The scope of the product

[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on internal temperature of the furnace displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 26. eLITHE platform requirement #25 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #25
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the temperature of the exhaust fumes.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the temperature of the exhaust fumes displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 27. eLITHE platform requirement #26 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #26
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the interior pressure of the furnace.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on interior pressure of the furnace displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 28. eLITHE platform requirement #27 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #27
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the temperature of the cooling water.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the temperature of the cooling water displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 29. eLITHE platform requirement #28 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #28
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the massflow of the cooling water
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the massflow of the cooling water displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 30. eLITHE platform requirement #29 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #29
[Description]	The Local Flexibility Markets (LFM) participation module will be given by the Decision Support System a certain amount of available power for trading and will return the matched power for a specific period of time and the price at which that power has been matched.
[Type]	The scope of the product

[Rationale]	Based on the marginal costs of the operation and on the foreseen operation curve, the unused power will be offered for LFM participation with a minimum remuneration per kWh at which the participation is profitable for the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	The module returns the basic data from the matching process (power, delivery time and price).
Priority	5
Comments	This functionality will be demonstrated at simulation level.
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 31. eLITHE platform requirement #30 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #30
[Description]	The TCID reduced DT will be integrated into a service that will handle simulation requests and will provide the corresponding simulation result to the module that requested it.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	This allows the other modules to communicate with the DT.
[Acceptance criteria]	The service is available and responding to the requests.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 32. eLITHE platform requirement #31 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #31
[Description]	The TCID-DT will provide the composition and temperature of the gas during the combustion phase.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Necessary to check that combustion is correct and that emissions are around acceptable levels.
[Acceptance criteria]	Numerical values in the right units are provided for the main gases: O ₂ , CO ₂ , CO, H ₂ O, NO _x .

Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 33. eLITHE platform requirement #32 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #32
[Description]	The TCID-DT will provide the average temperature of the load.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Necessary to check that the operating conditions in the furnace are correct.
[Acceptance criteria]	A numerical value in the right units is provided.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	TCID Pilot

Table 34. eLITHE platform requirement #33 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #33
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the electrical consumption of the furnace as a percentage of the nominal power.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The end-user/plant operator should always know the capacity factor of the furnace at each time.
[Acceptance criteria]	The load factor must be updated with a granularity of 1 minute.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 35. eLITHE platform requirement #34 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #34
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the material throughput of the furnace in real-time.

[Type]	The scope of the work
[Rationale]	Information required to calculate both average and instant power consumption
[Acceptance criteria]	A numerical value in the right units is provided.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 36. eLITHE platform requirement #35 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #35
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the temperature of the material exiting the furnace in real-time.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Temperature is the only parameter that can be monitored continuously and can be linked to the product quality.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the temperature of the final product displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 37. eLITHE platform requirement #36 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #36
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the massflow of the raw materials in kg/h
[Type]	The scope of the work
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the massflow of the final product displayed at all times.
Priority	5

Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot
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Table 38. eLITHE platform requirement #37 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #37
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the current microwave-emitted power output.
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the microwave-emitted power output displayed at all times.
Priority	4
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 39. eLITHE platform requirement #38 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #38
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the microwave absorption ratio
[Type]	Functional and data requirements
[Rationale]	The plant operator should constantly be able to monitor the S11 parameter (coefficient of reflection) of the microwave applicator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the microwave absorption ratio displayed at all times.
Priority	4
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 40. eLITHE platform requirement #39 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #39
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide the total electrical consumption of the furnace in kW in RT.
[Type]	The scope of the product

[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform's dashboard should provide useful and easy-to-read information to the plant operator.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on electricity consumption of the furnace displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 41. eLITHE platform requirement #40 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #40
[Description]	The eLITHE Platform should provide temperature values of the material inside the Kiln.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The plant operator should constantly be able to monitor direct or indirect values of the temperature of the material inside the kiln.
[Acceptance criteria]	RT data on the temperature values of the material inside the kiln displayed at all times.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 42. eLITHE platform requirement #41 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #41
[Description]	The Digital Twin will integrate the results of the simulation into the eLITHE platform.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	The eLITHE platform will compare the results of the simulations with the real data from demonstration activities.
[Acceptance criteria]	A certain parameter can be matched and compared
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 43. eLITHE platform requirement #42 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #42
[Description]	The ability of the eLITHE platform to visualise/present the integrated simulation results produced by the Digital Twin.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Easy and intuitive parameter check and decision-making.
[Acceptance criteria]	Visualise/present expected resulting value/curve/distribution, based on input value.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 44. eLITHE platform requirement #43 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #43
[Description]	The ability of the eLITHE platform to present in a comparative manner, simulation results and real-time variables.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Easy and intuitive parameter check and decision-making.
[Acceptance criteria]	Any form of visual/numerical comparison between simulated and real-time data.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 45. eLITHE platform requirement #44 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #44
[Description]	The ability of the eLITHE platform to monitor custom variables i.e. perform direct calculations between real-time variable values.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Adaptability and flexibility of the platform.

[Acceptance criteria]	At least ten available slots for custom variables.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 46. eLITHE platform requirement #45 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #45
[Description]	Ability of the eLITHE platform to store real-time data and visualise the evolution of variables over time.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	"Analysis of operation in case of transient conditions and possible improvement of Digital Twin model. Recovery of the stored data and analysis in case of failure/malfunction. "
[Acceptance criteria]	Basic data storage capability.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

Table 47. eLITHE platform requirement #46 characterisation table

[Requirement ID]	eLITHE platform requirement #46
[Description]	Ability of the eLITHE platform to export stored data for calibration and validation purposes.
[Type]	The scope of the product
[Rationale]	Digital Twin model improvement.
[Acceptance criteria]	Basic data export capability.
Priority	5
Pilot applicability	METLEN Pilot

3 eLITHE Platform's IT and data architecture

The data architecture diagram shows the flow of data between the different modules. The diagram is shown in Figure 5.

The data architecture is described from bottom to top as follows: first, the data will be retrieved from the plant through the RT monitor module, which will format the data and save it in the Operational DB and the Long-term DB. The *Operational DB* will always hold the last read value from the plant, while the Long-term DB will manage a history record of all the values. As illustrated in the diagram, the Operational DB will provide data to the user interface (to Dashboards and to the 3D Plant Visualization) and to the engine modules. Similarly, the Long-term DB will also provide data to the modules that require it. This communication between databases and different modules will be facilitated by backend services that will allow access to the databases. The communication services are not shown to simplify the diagram. Also, some arrows do not have the data description for simplicity and because sometimes no description is needed.

The engine modules will operate with the plant data stored in the databases and will also receive input from the users. The modules that will respond to user input are the following ones:

- The Digital Twin module will accept simulation requests from the UI and will calculate the requested simulation and make it available to the user.
- The Local flexibility markets participation module will send the user the possible explicit offers, and the user will be able to confirm the offers that should be executed and send them to the market.
- The Asset dispatcher will process the orders sent by the user and will write the corresponding values to the plant PLCs to actuate on the plant processes.

It is also worth explaining the communication process of the DSS. It will consume external data such as electricity tariffs and gas prices and the forecasts done in the Energy flexibility forecast module. With this data, it will calculate the optimal energy management strategy and it will send it to the UI module. Additionally, it will communicate with the Local flexibility markets participation module to indicate how much energy can be sent to the market. The market module will inform the DSS of the energy committed to the market once the user confirms the offer through the Market participation UI.

The presented data architecture is the general architecture of the platform, but it may be slightly modified for the different pilots if necessary (e.g., not all pilots may include the Video analysis module).

Figure 5. eLITHE Platform's IT and data architecture.

For comprehension purposes and in order to present the proposed eLITHE Platform's architecture in a *lighter* way, a schematic version of this architecture has also been developed focusing on functionalities and how these are going to be presented to the end-user (the industrial plant operator) via their associated graphic user interfaces. Additionally, the schematic version of the architecture also highlights the interconnection between the flexibility calculation-related modules, pointing out the necessary collaboration for integrated optimisation of the plant's potential to reduce cost and create additional revenue streams such as the flexibility provision to the electricity DSO.

The schematic version of the architecture, in coordination with the exploitation activities of WP7, identifies not only the core engines of the eLITHE Platform but also the partner responsible for their development, facilitating the early identification of responsibilities and the coordination of the Platform's exploitation strategies.

The schematic version of the architecture is displayed in Figure 6, where, from left to right, main data sources already identified are depicted and mapped as data provider to the Platform's engine as-a-whole. Each one of the engines points where its outcomes are addressed, either other engine modules or directly one of the Graphic User Interfaces (GUI).

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the eLITHE Platform's IT and data architecture

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4 Main modules and engines description and related data management strategies

4.1 Real-time monitor

The real-time monitoring module will consist of a set of microservices that will allow data to be retrieved from the plant's PLCs and devices and stored in the appropriate databases. There will be two main databases, the real-time database and the long-term database. The real-time database will be a MongoDB and the long-term database will be an InfluxDB. The real-time database will store the last values retrieved from the plant (the real-time values) and the platform data (dashboard configuration, users, etc.). The long-term database will store the historical readings, which will be necessary for many modules.

A microservice will be developed to retrieve the plant data from the PLCs. The data will be read from the PLCs using protocols such as opc-ua and modbus, depending on the compatibility of the PLCs. Once read, the data will be stored in both databases using a different microservice for each database. These microservices will format the data into the required data format and insert it in the DB (Table 48).

Table 48. Data flow for the real-time monitoring functionality

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Plant measurements from sensors (electrical consumption of the furnace, flow of natural gas, electric consumption of the electrodes, internal temperature of the furnace, etc.)	Formatted data stored in the databases.

4.2 KPI engine

The KPI engine is a module that takes advantage of the big data analytics features to calculate relevant indicators for the end-user. In the context of the eLITHE Platform, it will handle real-time calculation and display of the specific KPIs, among the ones defined in T2.1, that are of interest to the end-user for at-a-glance monitoring (Table 49).

The calculation of each one of those indicators will be implemented as an independent processing module that will take the data available in the long-term database as input. These modules will be regularly executed to calculate the required indicators according to the new

data available on the database, and will deliver results to three possible sinks, depending on the KPI being calculated:

- the operational database of the application for KPIs representing current status;
- the long-term database for KPIs indicating aggregations or trends;
- the internal Enterprise Service Bus (ESB) of the application for KPIs triggering further actions on other modules.

The objective of the KPI calculation modules using this technique is to preprocess information that will be further displayed by the Platform's GUI to providing behavioural system insights and assisting with decision-making.

Table 49. Data flow for the KPI engine functionality

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Electrical consumption of the furnace, nominal power of the furnace, flow of natural, flow of oxygen and pressure of the natural gas of each burner, mass flow of the raw materials and the final product in kg/h, electric consumption of the electrodes, the induction systems and the auxiliary equipment, internal temperature of the furnace, temperature of the exhaust fumes, interior pressure of the furnace, temperature of the cooling water, mass flow of the cooling water, BESS charging status, etc.	Set of for KPIs' values representing current status in real-time. Timeseries of values to be stored in the long-term Influx DB for the KPIs indicating aggregations or trends and their values upon request for the identified evaluation periods. KPI values through the ESB for the KPIs triggering further actions on other modules.

4.3 Forecasting module

The forecasting module will work on a twofold approach:

- On the flexibility forecasting module will provide individual forecasted parameters, which will be displayed in a disaggregated manner on the eLITHE Platform's dashboard.
- On the calculation of additional variables that may be of interest to the plant operator and that have not been considered under the flexibility forecasting scope.

The forecasting module will serve both as a forecast generator and as a gateway for the pre-calculated variables.

Table 50. Data flow for the forecasting module

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Plant measurements data. Flexibility forecast module outcomes	Forecasts.

4.4 Assets dispatcher

The Asset Dispatcher module is the eLITHE Platform software module in charge of executing the appropriate schedule of the controllable assets (i.e., the electrified furnaces but also others if applicable) by continuously comparing the actual setpoint executed by the assets with the planned one based on the inputs from the DSS and the DT as well as the LFM participation module). The corresponding commands to configure the appropriate setpoints are triggered whenever deemed required, upon detection of a mismatch between the schedule and the status or a required change based on that schedule (Table 51).

This mechanism therefore builds the bridge between the modules composing the optimum schedule for the different assets of the building (the DSS operated by the SO, which builds a baseline schedule focused on minimizing the cost, and the flexibility forecast module, updating the baseline schedule in order to meet the constraints imposed by the schedule and validated or modified by the plant operator).

Table 51. Data flow for the assets dispatcher functionality

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Permissions to write values to the PLCs	The ability to control the plant assets from the platform

4.5 Predictive maintenance module

The predictive maintenance module aims to identify potential failures in specific components or elements of the installation by implementing AI-based algorithms to monitor previously defined parameters (e.g., temperature or vibrations) that are critical to the component or element's correct performance.

The module, integrated into the eLITHE Platform, would inform the plant operator of potential risks based on the state of health of the identified components or elements. This state of health will be divided into risk levels based on monitoring and data analytics of the selected parameters subject to be studied in the predictive maintenance use case.

Figure 7 showcases an example of how the graphic user interface could present, for one element or component, the identified risks and their storage over time.

Figure 7. Alarm identification and recording over time for one element or component.

For the case of an installation where there are multiple components monitored in parallel, the eLITHE Platform will also provide a graphic user interface for the plant operator to visualise them all at a glance similarly to Figure 8:

Figure 8. Alarm identification and recording over time for a set of elements or components.

The predictive maintenance module requires different data for each pilot depending on the elements to be analysed and their respective critical parameters to be monitored and studied. Table 52 shows some datasets provided by the pilots that could be used for such purpose.

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Table 52. Data flow for the predictive maintenance module

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
<p>Historical operational data for training Real-time operational data for prediction</p>	<p>State of health of the components Maintenance alarms</p>
<p>The required data for the Spanish pilot are: production rate, external refractory surface temperature, specific consumption, auger motor RPMs, interior pressure of the furnace, temperature of the exhaust, temperature of the furnace, temperature of the induction system, temperature of the electrodes, current of the electrodes, current of the induction system, frit extraction system electric consumption, temperature of the burners, pressure of the natural gas of each burner, flow of oxygen of each burner, exchanger differential pressure, filter differential pressure, fans speed, fans vibration, etc.</p>	
<p>Required data for the Greek pilot are: temperature of process (solid and gases), microwave power, ; flow rates; pressure drop of the valves; pressure and flow speed of the compressed air circuit elements; temperature and vibrations of the kiln; temperature of the joins; temperature, sound, vibration and pressure of the extractors; vibration, speed and electrical consumption of the conveying system; energy consumption and water temperature of the chiller; pressure and temperature of the water circuit; leakage, temperature of the generator; electric arc presence ; water temperature and signal quality of the isolator; microwave signal parametres; speed, torque and current consumption of the feeder; suction pressure and vibrations of the bag filter; temperature, flow and pressure drop of the pipes; etc.</p>	
<p>The required RT data for the German pilot are temperatures of exhaust, kiln atmosphere, recirculation gas through the top channel, and electrical heating element. Current through the electrical heating element.</p>	

4.6 Safety and plant security monitoring and control module

The Safety and Plant Security Monitoring and Control Module will be designed to ensure the safety and security of an industrial facility. It will continuously monitor sensors, parameters and alarms defined as critical for the electrical furnace, detecting and alerting on any

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abnormal value. It will also log incidents for further analysis and can integrate coordination with external devices (e.g., phone calls and automated emails or SMSs).

A set of parameters will be identified as critical to be monitored and alongside there will be certain upper and lower thresholds where the normal value will be fluctuating within (Table 53). If any abnormal value is detected, predefined protocols will be activated either automatically or through notification to the Plant operator.

Table 53. Data flow for the safety and plant security monitoring and control module

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Real-time monitoring data of the plant (flow of oxygen and pressure of the natural gas of each burner, internal temperature of the furnace, temperature of the exhaust fumes, interior pressure of the furnace, etc.)	Abnormal value detection alarms.

4.7 Energy flexibility forecast

This module will generate 24h forecasts of thermal energy demand and local solar generation based on historic hourly data and the production plan for the day ahead to model the technical behaviour of the thermal system with a twofold objective:

- (i) calculation of optimal operation setpoints of manageable systems, which will be taken as a baseline or reference, and
- (ii) calculation of the possibilities of variation of this optimal operation and associated cost, which will be taken as an evaluation of the flexibility by the DSS tool.

The outputs, the baseline and the flexibility possibilities (the capacity to increase or reduce the overall consumption of the installation), will be used by the DSS module and the asset dispatcher to enable participation in flexibility markets, supporting electricity grid operators (Table 54).

Table 54. Data flow for the energy flexibility forecast module

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Production plan per hour (t/h) The full-year production plan in t/h, including the recipe.	Energy demand forecasts (kW): The production throughput in real-time and the forecast for the short-term ahead.
Historic energy demand time series (kW) Time series of thermal energy demand per hour.	RES Generation forecasts (kW): The short-term forecast of electricity generated from renewable sources per hour in the day ahead.
Historic energy generation time series (kW) Time series of PV energy generation per hour.	Energy surplus (kW) Difference between energy generation forecast and energy demand forecast
State of Charge BESS (% , kWh)	Energy flexibility available (kW)

Most recent state of charge of the BESS	Amount of energy available for flexibility upwards (store energy) or downwards (consume energy from storage)
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4.8 Decision support system

Based on the results of the flexibility assessment done in T2.2, the most promising sources of energy flexibility in the industrial processes are energy storage (TES and BESS), production rate variations and the dual combination of gas/hydrogen combustion with electricity heating. The DSS will make hourly energy assessments for the 24 hours ahead according to the production plan and the RES generation and thermal process demand forecasts generated by the Energy Flexibility Forecast algorithm. An optimal energy management scenario that minimizes the hourly energy costs will be provided by evaluating day-ahead hourly energy costs and the status and cost of the available flexibility sources. This assessment is generated every hour as new process data and refined forecasts become available, and will be displayed graphically to the operation manager to make the final decision on how the energy is consumed. The difference in energy costs between the optimal energy management scenario and the default scenario reflects the savings achieved by adopting the recommended optimal scenario. The DSS will also provide an assessment of flexibility potential and the cost, to the Local Flexibility Markets Participation module, to be traded in qualified markets in exchange for a market external remuneration. The committed flexibility offered at a future flexibility event (power, time and duration of the event) should also be fed back in order to block this flexibility and prevent it from being consumed otherwise (Table 55).

Table 55. Data flow for the decision support system

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Productivity (kg/h): The production throughput in real-time and the forecast for the short-term ahead.	Optimal energy management: Strategy for the optimal distribution of energy resources minimising the costs of energy usage in the 24 hours ahead. Operation costs: Detailed calculation of the default scenario cost and the optimal energy scenario of the day ahead, taking into account current tariffs and the use of stored energy and flexibility sources.
RES Generation (kWh): The short-term forecast of electricity generated from renewable sources per hour in the day ahead.	
Electricity storage (kWh): Total and available battery storage capacity. Real-time state of charge of the BESS.	
Thermal storage (kWh): Total and available thermal storage capacity and the real-time TES status.	

H ₂ storage (kg): Quantity of hydrogen available for consumption in real-time, generation capacity and process costs.	Hour ahead flexibility potential assessment and cost of delivery.
Gas prices (€/kWh LHV) Gas tariff per unit of LHV	
H ₂ production amount (kg/h) and costs (€/kg) 24h ahead hydrogen generation plan and cost per hour.	
Electricity tariff (€/kWh) 24 hours ahead of electricity cost per hour.	
Committed explicit flexibility in external local flexibility markets (kW) Flexibility event time and duration (hour, min)	

4.9 Digital twin modules

4.9.1 Digital twin of the Spanish Pilot furnace

The DT is a digital representation of the core process that accepts some inputs and returns some outputs in response. This digital representation is essentially a piece of software which is provided in a format appropriate for its integration into the platform.

The DT contains a reduced order model (ROM) of the core process. The ROM is a set of mathematical relationships between the inputs and the outputs that allow the obtention of the latter in essentially real-time. Building the ROM (i.e., fitting the free parameters of the mathematical model) is necessary to have many data featuring the desired inputs and outputs. When both can be measured those data come from historical records, but in some cases, we are interested in outputs which are not measurable.

When the outputs cannot be measured, realistic physics-driven simulations can be used. This is the approach to be used in TCID. The furnace for frits melting is modelled using CFD (computational fluid dynamics). Once a simulation model is obtained and validated many simulations are run representing different scenarios. The scenarios are defined depending on the selected inputs and their ranges of variation. After simulating the scenarios, the inputs and outputs can be correlated using different models (i.e., parametric fitting, Kriging method, non-parametric regression or neural networks) to obtain the best fitting, measured by a goodness-of-fit function.

Finally, the ROM is exported to a file that can be easily shared, i.e., an FMU (Functional Mockup Unit).

In the case of TCID, the requirements defined for the DT are:

- The Digital Twin will integrate the results of the simulation into the eLITHE platform.

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- Ability of the eLITHE platform to visualise/present the integrated simulation results produced by the digital twin.
- The TCID-DT will provide the composition and temperature of the gas during the combustion phase.
- The TCID-DT will provide the average temperature of the load.

The complete list of inputs and outputs will be defined at a later stage when the CFD model is more developed and is possible to assess which outputs can be calculated.

4.9.2 Digital Twin of the Greek Pilot Furnace

The Digital Twin (DT) of the Greek Pilot furnace corresponds to a complete Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model of the alumina calcination furnace that will be installed within the premises of METLEN. The CFD model that is currently under development is based on technical directives by CEI, the manufacturer of the physical furnace unit. The DT of the furnace, i.e. the finalised CFD model, will be able to simulate the operation of the electrically powered, microwave (MW) calciner and compute the final state of the system based on the input data. The minimum input data that is needed for the simulations to run is described in Table 56 at the end of this paragraph. The numerical simulations will take place using the ANSYS-Fluent CFD software [2]. In-house developed code (UDFs) is expected to be used within the ANSYS-Fluent environment for the description of the calcination process with the use of microwaves. The CFD model will utilise a transient pressure-based solver, species transport equations will be solved for the gaseous phases, while gibbsite, the solid working material, will be modelled with the use of the Discrete Phase Model (DPM). A depiction of the gibbsite flow within a cylindrical furnace based on a preliminary model set-up is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Gibbsite particle flow within a cylindrical furnace. Preliminary results.

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The numerical simulations that will take place are computationally intensive calculations with a total runtime of several weeks. It is, therefore, scheduled that all calculations will be performed in advance and, subsequently, the results will be loaded to the eLITHE platform. More specifically, the completed version of the DT model will be used to simulate a range of operating conditions and produce the corresponding solution files. The ANSYS-Fluent-produced solution files will contain the values of all the variables of interest to the project. It must be noted that the solution files are large (usually several gigabytes each) and they can not be directly manipulated within the eLITHE platform. Thus, all the needed variable values will be exported in text format files, the data will be structured as vectors or matrices and loaded to the eLITHE platform. Each output data set will correspond to a specific set of input (operating) conditions (Table 56). Thus, with the use of the DT results, a mapping between input and output conditions can be created.

Table 56. Data flow for the DT of the METLEN Pilot furnace

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Furnace angle (if adjustable)	Temperature distribution on furnace walls
Furnace rotational speed (if adjustable)	Temperature distribution of solid material along the furnace length
Inlet mass flow rate of air/gas (if applicable)	Average load temperature within the furnace
Inlet mass flow rate of solid material	Average solid particle residence time
Inlet temperature of solid material	Average mass fraction rate of water vapour at the outlet
Mean particle diameter of solid material	
Power of applied electromagnetic field	
Material loss factor as a function of temperature (if available)	Notes:
Magnitude of electric field within the furnace (if available)	1. The list of extracted data can be extended if the requested variables can be calculated by the CFD model
Outlet temperature of solid material (control data)	2. All output data will be available in text format files, structured as vectors or matrices

4.10 Local Flexibility Markets Participation Module

The local flexibility markets participation module to be integrated into the eLITHE Platform will be based on the service developed by ETRA at the STREAM Project [3] for large flexibility assets to participate in the Local Flexibility Market (LFM) established by the Nominated Electricity Market Operator (NEMO) in the Iberian electricity system.

The main aim of the service is to provide flexibility and enable bidding in the LFM. The eLITHE Platform will offer the flexibility calculated and made available by the DSS and the DT to the market, either for services to the DSO via an LFM or for peer-to-peer transactions in bilateral markets.

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An additional service simulating the opening and clearing of a Local Flexibility Market will be set up based on actual results coming mainly from STREAM, as the first sandbox implementation of LFMs in the Iberian electricity system (Table 57).

The eLITHE Platform will coordinate the operation of the assets that have been selected to fulfill the bids while maintaining the quality of the service. The whole process, from asset planning to revenue calculation, is managed by the Platform and its internal services (e.g., the assets dispatcher).

Table 57. Data flow for the Local Flexibility Markets participation module

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
Available flexibility from the controlled assets Cost of the flexibility activation Market prices and results of the market clearing process	Communication to the DSS and the plant operator on the assets and power activated. Actuation/(de)activation over the assets

4.11 Computer Vision for furnaces monitoring

The computer vision tools developed within this project will enable real-time monitoring of critical parameters—temperature and volume—during the melting process of frits in the TCID system. Since the quality of the produced frits depends on the melting temperature, controlling these parameters is essential for ensuring product quality.

Currently, the melting process relies on measuring the furnace atmosphere temperature, which does not accurately reflect the temperature of the feedstock itself. The proposed computer vision system will address this limitation by directly measuring the feedstock temperature, providing detailed insights into temperature variations across the molten area inside the kiln.

Additionally, the feedstock volume is a key indicator of the degree of melting within the kiln. At present, this parameter is assessed visually by operators, who then adjust process settings based on their observations. The computer vision system will automate this process by using advanced machine learning and deep learning algorithms to evaluate the molten frit's status in real-time, while providing the value of the volume to the furnace control system. The system will integrate a thermal infrared camera and an RGB camera, although a single-camera solution may be implemented if its specifications meet the algorithmic requirements. Both cameras will be housed in a cooled, protective enclosure to ensure durability in harsh environments. A viewing port with clear visual access to the melting feedstock will be installed to capture high-quality images needed for algorithm development and implementation (Table 58).

Table 58. Data flow for the Computer Vision for furnaces monitoring module

(Minimum) Input data needed	Expected output data / results
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<p>Images of the feedstock are obtained through a viewing port with access inside the furnace.</p>	<p>Frits temperature. Volume of feedstock (measurement method to be defined, e.g., levels, area in the image) Video streaming of the processed images</p>
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5 First approach towards the data management strategy for the Pilots

Given the different nature of the pilots and their data management preferences, a different data management strategy will be followed for each pilot.

5.1 Spanish Pilot Site

The Spanish pilot's developed frit smelter will operate at an industrial scale, comprising a substantial number of components, including induction and electrode heating, auxiliary gas heating, and water quenching of the material. This pilot site will have many components digitalized and connected to PLCs, from which the data will be retrieved and subsequently saved in databases. The minimum data to be retrieved will be in accordance with the specified requirements. However, additional data may be included as the project progresses and becomes available.

TCID will provide the IT infrastructure, situated within its own facilities, for the deployment of the platform. All software will be deployed at their facilities, with databases located in the TCID data centre and engine modules deployed on plant servers. In this way, the platform will operate entirely within their network. TCID will provide remote access to their IT infrastructure to test and deploy the modules to be developed.

5.2 Greek Pilot Site

In the Greek pilot, the data of process are obtained from the PLC that will control the complex microwave-based calciner, using a real-time specific monitoring and control system for the microwave tuning. Pre-processed collected data from PLC will be sent to the remote server via the Internet. The real-time monitor module will be fed with the data obtained from the PLC. The necessary hardware for executing the real-time monitor module and communicating with the external server will be deployed directly at the pilot site. The required process data will be stored and processed within the remote server and displayed on the platform.

5.3 German Pilot Site

The data management strategy for the German Pilot is expected to be identical to the approach used for the Greek Pilot. However, as the control cabinet for the electrified furnace and other furnace-specific control systems (that may limit the system's data-sharing capabilities) are still under definition at the time of this document's delivery, the specific data management strategy will be revisited and presented during WP3 development, when the actual connection between the Platform and the field equipment will be established.

6 Conclusions

Deliverable *D2.3 ICT requirements and data management of the pilots* presents a comprehensive approach for developing and implementing the digital solutions to manage the electrified industrial processes on the basis of the eLITHE Platform development. The technical requirements section outlines the essential requisites to ensure the tool delivers optimal functionality and user experience, addressing the needs of plant operators. By addressing these requirements early and following the well-known and validated Volere methodology, the document establishes a clear path for development, minimizing potential obstacles and aligning with stakeholder expectations.

The IT and data architecture section provides a detailed blueprint of the system's infrastructure, emphasizing interoperability with legacy and newly designed equipment, while mapping data sources, storage services, the Platform's main engines and detailing how information will be presented to the end-user through graphic user interfaces.

Each module is described, highlighting its specific role and contribution to the overall system. This modular approach facilitates targeted development and testing, enabling teams to focus on individual components while maintaining a cohesive system design. It also allows for easier updates and enhancements, as modules can be modified or added independently without needing to modify the entire system.

The data management strategies section outlines methods for handling data efficiently and securely, tailored to the specific needs of each industrial installation.

Overall, this deliverable serves as a comprehensive guide for the eLITHE Platform's development and implementation, handing over the next steps to *WP3 Digitalization, control and flexibility tools (including TES) of the electrification processes*. By addressing technical, architectural, and data management aspects, this document sets a solid foundation for the kick-off of the upcoming development activities.

7 References

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